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Studies on Some Mixed-ligand Complexes of Tin Tetrachloride

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In continuation to our studies on mixed-ligand complexes¹ we wish to report synthesis and characterisation of a few more hitherto unknown complexes of similar general formula $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{LL}'$ (L = dimethyl formamide (DMF), dimethyl acetamide (DMA), dimethyl propionamide (DMP), or diphenylformamide (DPF); L' = pyridine N-oxide (PyO) or lutidine N-oxide (TNO)). Possible structure of the complexes is suggested.

Experimental

Materials: Commercially available tin tetrachloride was used after distillation. DMF, DMA, DMP, DPF, PyO and LNO were obtained from Fischer Scientific U. S. A. and used as such.

Preparation of complexes: The mixed-ligand complexes were prepared according to one of the following methods:

(i) Displacement reaction:

In a representative experiment a solution of 2 m moles of $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{DMF}$ in 10 ml. acetonitrile was treated with an equimolar quantity of PyO in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed for about two hours and the excess solvent was distilled off. The residual solution on treatment with diethyl ether yielded a white crystalline solid which was filtered, washed and dried in vacuum.

(ii) Adduct formation:

A solution of 5 m moles of tin tetrachloride in 10 ml carbon tetrachloride was treated with an equimolar mixture of DMF and PyO (5 m mole each) in 10 ml of the same solvent with constant stirring. The precipitated white crystalline solid was identical to that obtained through displacement reaction.

The experimental results are collected in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The newly synthesised compounds are white crystalline solid having poor solubility in organic solvents. They are non-electrolytes, thermally stable and unaffected by atmospheric moisture and oxygen.

The IR spectral data show a distinct negative shift of the C=O stretching frequency and a slight positive shift of the NCO bending mode from their position in the free ligands, in agreement to the observations of previous workers²⁻⁵, and indicate the coordination from the oxygen atom of the amide molecule to the tin atom. The presence of coordinated N=O ligands through the oxygen atom is indicated from the following⁶⁻⁹:

(a) The N=O str. mode around $1185 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is distinctly shifted to lower frequency region as compared to that in the free bases.

(b) The N=O bending mode appears at $832 \pm 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. Its location is not very different from that in the corresponding bases which is in agreement to the observations and explanations of several previous workers.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL RESULTS AND IR ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) FOR $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{LL}'$

L	L'	Sn	Analysis % obs. (calcd.)			N	IR absorption frequencies (cm^{-1})					
			C	H	N		Amide I band $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\delta(\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$	$\delta(\text{N}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$
DMF	PyO	26.80	20.30	2.82	6.40	1610 m	670 vs	1180 s	830 vs	780 vs	400 m	
		(27.71)	(20.21)	(2.81)	(6.31)						330 m	
DMA	PyO	26.40	24.62	3.38	6.50	1610 m	675 vs	1180 m	830 vs	780 vs	390 m	
		(26.80)	(24.38)	(3.19)	(6.25)						335 m	
DMP	PyO	25.60	28.20	3.78	6.00	1620 vs	670 s	1190 m	835 sh	775 vs	390 vs	
		(25.28)	(28.02)	(3.80)	(5.98)						310 m	
DPF	PyO	21.90	39.30	3.44	5.50	1615 m	690 m	1190 m	830 vs	775 s	390 vs	
		(21.58)	(39.04)	(3.80)	(5.38)						320 m	
DMF	LNO	26.00	26.28	3.80	6.80	1610 m	710 m	1185 s	832 m	790 s	410 w	
		(26.04)	(26.20)	(3.58)	(6.59)						380 s	
DMA	LNO	25.60	28.03	3.58	5.58	1615 m	700 m	1190 m	835 m	790 s	400 m	
		(25.28)	(28.02)	(3.80)	(5.90)						380 m	
DMP	LNO	23.60	31.50	4.80	5.50	1620 m	680 m	1182 s	832 m	780 s	390 m	
		(23.70)	(31.19)	(4.58)	(5.00)						320 w	
DPF	LNO	20.80	41.60	3.60	4.60	1612 m	690 vs	1180 m	834 vs	790 vs	410 w	
		(20.48)	(41.38)	(3.48)	(4.80)						375 m	

(c) The C—H out of plane deformation mode identified at $782 \pm 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ shows a positive shift due to tightening of the aromatic ring on complexation.

The two absorptions close to each other in the range $400 - 310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been attributed to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$ giving unequivocal support to coordination through the oxygen atoms of the ligands. The appearance of two Sn—O str. modes is an indication of the different bond strength of the Sn—O linkages, consequently suggesting different basicity of the two donor molecules.

Since in hexa coordinated adducts of tin tetrachloride of the formula $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{L}$, the two monodentate bases occupy *cis* position, the displacement of one of the ligands by another strong base is not expected to produce a major change in the stereochemistry of the adducts.

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New Stable Vanadium(III) Chelates of Some Pyridine Carboxylic Acids

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TRIVALENT vanadium chelates stable in laboratory atmosphere in solid state as well as in solution are of rare occurrence¹⁻³. The present study is

undertaken as a part of our programme on stabilization of normally unstable oxidation states of transition metal ions through ligation to suitable donor molecules. Three extremely stable vanadium(III) complexes of pyridine-2-carboxylic acid, pyridine-2, 6-dicarboxylic acid and pyridine-2, 4, 6-tricarboxylic acid are obtained in the solid state. Hot aqueous solution of the ligands (3.25 m moles) are treated with solid VCl_3 (1 m mole) and stirred vigorously when the following compounds are obtained in good yield:

The compounds are washed with boiled out water and alcohol nearly dried under suction and kept over fused calcium chloride for 48 hours.

Elemental analysis is in accordance with the proposed formulation and is given along with the magnetic moment values at room temperature in Table 1. All the three compounds are stable towards oxidation in the solid state. Solutions of the complexes in boiled out water containing small quantities of the appropriate ligands are fairly stable as is indicated from the unchanged nature of their absorption spectra even after two hours. All the compounds can be recrystallised from concentrated aqueous solutions containing some ligand.

Magnetic moment values at room temperature (300°K) given in Table 1 indicate the presence of two unpaired electrons^{4,5} in all of them. Electronic spectra of the complexes in alcohol and in water in presence of a small amount of the appropriate ligand exhibit two electronic transitions [$27000-25000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$: ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$; $13900-12000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$: ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$] which are indicative of an octahedral disposition of the donor sites around the $d^3 \text{ V(III)}$ species^{1,2,6,7}.

I.R. spectra of the ligand and the complexes were monitored in the $4000-250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region in CsBr-matrix. Both pyridine-2, 6-dicarboxylic acid and pyridine-2, 4, 6-tricarboxylic acid exhibited the $-\text{COO}$ stretch as a strong band at $1720-1715 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region and pyridine-2-carboxylic acid exhibited the same stretching mode at 1710 cm^{-1} . In the I.R. spectra of the complexes this $1720-1710 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ band is shifted towards lower wave number region ($1675-1665 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) which is indicative of bonding through the carboxyl moiety⁸.

In pyridine derivatives the two bands at $600-640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (in plane ring deformation) and at $400-415 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (out of plane ring deformation) are